

Association between Position of Post-Partum Intrauterine Device (PPIUCD) as Detected by Immediate Sonography and Expulsion Rate at 6-Weeks and 12-Weeks

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Abstract:

Background: The postpartum period is a critical time for initiating effective contraception to prevent unintended pregnancies and promote maternal health. Intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCDs), particularly the copper T device, are favored for their long-term efficacy and minimal maintenance. However, the expulsion of postpartum IUCDs (PPIUCDs) remains a significant concern, potentially compromising their effectiveness. This study aims to investigate the association between the expulsion of PPIUCDs at 6 weeks and 12 weeks post-insertion and their location as confirmed by ultrasonography.

Methods: This was a prospective cohort study of 100 postpartum women who underwent normal vaginal delivery followed by PPIUCD placement was studied. IUCD positioning was confirmed via ultrasonography and expulsion rates were recorded at 6- and 12-weeks post-insertion.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 25.3 years. 67 IUCDs were correctly positioned at the fundus and 33 mispositioned (11 lower, 11 lateral, and 11 mid-cavity). At 6 weeks, 5 women experienced IUCD expulsion, with 4 of these expulsions occurring in mid-cavity positions. By 12 weeks, an additional 9 expulsions were recorded, distributed across various mispositions. Statistical analysis revealed a significant association between IUCD location and expulsion rates, while age and parity were not significantly associated with expulsion.

Conclusion: The study highlights the critical role of IUCD location in determining expulsion rates. Ensuring correct fundal placement and routine ultrasonographic follow-up can significantly improve the success rates of PPIUCDs, enhancing postpartum contraception efficacy and reducing unintended pregnancies.

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Introduction

The postpartum period presents a critical window for initiating effective contraception to prevent unintended pregnancies and optimize maternal health. Intrauterine contraceptive devices (IUCDs), particularly the copper T device, have emerged as a popular choice due to their long-term efficacy and minimal maintenance requirements. However, the expulsion of postpartum IUCDs remains a significant concern, potentially undermining their effectiveness. This research aims to explore the association between the expulsion of postpartum IUCDs and their location as confirmed by ultrasonography.

The insertion of IUCDs immediately after childbirth, known as postpartum IUCD (PPIUCD) insertion, offers several advantages, including convenience and high motivation for contraception among new mothers [1]. Despite these benefits, the expulsion rates of PPIUCDs are notably higher compared to interval insertions, which occur

several weeks postpartum [2]. The timing of insertion, type of delivery, and the specific type of IUCD used are critical factors influencing expulsion rates [3]. Immediate postpartum insertions, particularly within 10 minutes of placental delivery, have been associated with higher expulsion rates compared to insertions performed after the puerperium [4].

Ultrasonography plays a pivotal role in confirming the correct placement of IUCDs and identifying cases of partial or complete expulsion. Studies have demonstrated that the location of the IUCD within the uterine cavity, as visualized by ultrasonography, is a significant predictor of expulsion risk [5]. Properly positioned IUCDs, typically located at the fundus of the uterus, are less likely to be expelled compared to those positioned lower in the uterine cavity [6]. This highlights the importance of accurate placement during insertion

and the potential need for follow-up imaging to ensure optimal positioning.

The relationship between IUCD location and expulsion is further complicated by the type of delivery. Vaginal deliveries have been associated with higher expulsion rates compared to cesarean sections. This disparity may be attributed to the differences in uterine involution and the mechanical forces exerted during vaginal delivery. Additionally, the type of IUCD used, whether copper or levonorgestrel-releasing, also influences expulsion rates, with copper IUCDs generally exhibiting lower expulsion rates.

This research seeks to elucidate the association between the expulsion of PPIUCDs at 6 weeks and 12 weeks post-insertion and their location as confirmed by ultrasonography. By analyzing data from a cohort of postpartum women who received IUCDs, this study aims to identify key factors contributing to expulsion and provide evidence-based recommendations for clinical practice. Understanding these associations is crucial for improving the efficacy of postpartum contraception and reducing the incidence of unintended pregnancies.

In conclusion, while PPIUCDs offer a convenient and effective contraceptive option for postpartum women, the risk of expulsion remains a significant challenge. Ultrasonography provides a valuable tool for confirming IUCD placement and identifying those at risk of expulsion. This research will contribute to the existing body of knowledge by exploring the intricate relationship between IUCD location and expulsion at 6 weeks and 12 weeks post-insertion, ultimately aiming to enhance the success rates of postpartum IUCD insertions

Materials and Methods

Study Design: It is a hospital based prospective observational study conducted from June 2019-June 2020 at Department of Obstetrics and

Gynaecology, Mahila Chikitsalaya, SMS Medical College, Jaipur. All women who delivered by normal vaginal mode and are eligible and willing for PPIUCD were included in the study. Women having extrauterine placement of PPIUCD were excluded.

Sample size: It is calculated at 95% confidence level assuming 62% malposition of IUCD in cases of vaginal delivery as per a previous study [7] at the absolute allowable error of 10%. 100 cases were taken into study expecting 10% dropouts in follow-up period.

Data Collection: IUCD was inserted after normal vaginal delivery (Post placental insertion) with informed consent. Ultrasonographic (USG) examination was done within 48 hours of normal delivery to check position of IUCD. Follow up visits were done at 6 weeks and 12 weeks and women were evaluated for expulsion by history, examination or USG. Women who were complaining with pain abdomen and willing for removal of IUCD, were counselled adequately and given supportive treatment and motivated to continue with the IUCD. In case of missing thread, ultrasonography was additionally done to confirm if the IUCD was in-utero or expelled out.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed with the Stata v12.0. The Categorical data was presented as numbers (frequency) and were compared among groups using Chi square test. The quantitative data was presented as mean and standard deviation and were compared by students t-test. P-value was considered to be significant if less than 0.05.

The ethical clearance of the study was obtained from Institutional Ethics Committee.

Results

Mean age of the study population was 25.2 years and most of the women had parity of one (Table 1).

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of the study population

Variables	Mean (SD)/ n (%)
Age	25.2 (3.5)
BMI	24.7 (2.2)
Parity	
P1	44
P2	20
≥P3	36
IUCD location	
Fundal position (Correct)	67 (67%)
Lateral	11 (11%)
Lower	11 (11%)
Mid-cavity	11 (11%)
IUCD expulsion at 6 weeks	
Yes	5 (5%)
No	95 (95%)

IUCD expulsion at 12 weeks	
Yes	14 (14%)
No	86 (86%)

67% IUCD were in correct position while 33% were mispositioned. On follow-up, 5% of the women had IUCD expulsion at 6 weeks which increased to 14% at 12 weeks. Of the five expelled at 6 weeks, four were in mid-cavity position. Out of the nine IUCD expelled between 6-12 weeks,

majority (5) were from lateral or lower position. Further analysis found only IUCD location or misposition to be statistically significantly associated with IUCD expulsion both at 6 weeks and 12 weeks (Table 2 and 3).

Table 2. Association of IUCD expulsion at 6 weeks with the baseline characteristics and IUCD location

	In-situ (n=95)	Expelled (n=5)	p-value
Age	25.2 (3.5)	25 (3.3)	0.91
BMI	24.7 (2.2)	23.9 (2.9)	0.38
Parity			
P1	43 (97.7%)	1 (2.3%)	0.465
P2	29 (95.0%)	1 (5.0%)	
≥P3	33 (91.7%)	3 (8.3%)	
IUCD location			
Fundal (Correct)	66 (98.5%)	1 (1.5%)	0.003
Lateral	11 (100%)	0 (0%)	
Lower	11 (100%)	0 (0%)	
Mid-cavity	7 (63.6%)	4 (36.4%)	

Table 3. Association of IUCD expulsion at 12 weeks with the baseline characteristics and IUCD location

	In-situ (n=86)	Expelled (n=14)	p-value
Age	25.4 (3.6)	23.9 (2.8)	0.13
BMI	24.8 (2.2)	24.0 (2.3)	0.19
Parity			
P1	39 (88.6%)	5 (11.4%)	0.653
P2	16 (80.0%)	4 (20.0%)	
≥P3	31 (86.1%)	5 (13.9%)	
IUCD location			
Fundal	63 (94.0%)	4 (6.0%)	0.002
Lateral	8 (72.7%)	3 (27.3%)	
Lower	9 (81.8%)	2 (18.2%)	
Mid-cavity	6 (54.6%)	5 (45.4%)	

Discussion

The findings of this study provide significant insights into the factors influencing the expulsion of postpartum intrauterine contraceptive devices (PPIUCDs), particularly focusing on the role of IUCD location as confirmed by ultrasonography. The study's results underscore the critical importance of accurate IUCD placement in minimizing expulsion rates, thereby enhancing the efficacy of postpartum contraception.

The overall expulsion rate observed in this study aligns with existing literature, which reports higher expulsion rates for PPIUCDs compared to interval insertions. The expulsion rate at 6 weeks was 5%, with an additional 9% expulsion rate observed between 6 and 12 weeks. This cumulative expulsion rate of 14% is consistent with previous studies that have reported expulsion rates ranging from 10% to 20% for PPIUCDs [1,8].

A key finding of this study is the significant association between IUCD location and expulsion rates. At the 6-week follow-up, 80% of the expulsions occurred in women with IUCDs initially positioned in the mid-cavity, highlighting the vulnerability of non-fundal placements. This trend continued at the 12-week follow-up, where expulsions were distributed across various mispositions, including lateral and lower positions. These findings corroborate previous research indicating that IUCDs positioned at the fundus are less likely to be expelled compared to those located lower in the uterine cavity [9,10].

The statistical analysis revealed that IUCD location was the only factor significantly associated with expulsion at both 6 and 12 weeks. Neither age nor parity showed a significant correlation with expulsion rates. This is an important observation, as it suggests that clinical efforts should prioritize

ensuring correct fundal placement of IUCDs during insertion, regardless of the patient's age or parity. The use of ultrasonography immediately post-insertion and during follow-up visits could be instrumental in confirming proper placement and reducing expulsion rates.

The study's findings have important clinical implications. First, they emphasize the need for training healthcare providers in the correct technique for IUCD insertion, with a focus on achieving fundal placement. Second, the results suggest that routine ultrasonographic confirmation of IUCD position could be beneficial, particularly in the immediate postpartum period. This approach could help identify and correct mispositions before they result in expulsion, thereby improving the overall success rates of PPIUCDs.

Moreover, the study highlights the potential benefits of follow-up visits at 6 and 12 weeks postpartum. These visits provide opportunities to monitor IUCD position and address any issues early, thereby reducing the likelihood of expulsion. Given the significant association between IUCD location and expulsion, follow-up visits should include ultrasonographic evaluation to ensure the device remains correctly positioned.

The study's limitations include its relatively small sample size and the single-center design, which may limit the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the study did not account for other potential confounding factors such as breastfeeding status, which could influence expulsion rates. Future studies with larger, multi-center cohorts and consideration of additional variables are needed to validate and expand upon these findings.

Overall, this research contributes to the existing body of knowledge by highlighting the importance of IUCD location in preventing expulsion and ensuring the success of postpartum contraception. By focusing on accurate placement and routine follow-up, healthcare providers can significantly improve the outcomes for women opting for PPIUCDs, ultimately enhancing maternal health and reducing the risk of unintended pregnancies.

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